

WOMEN'S COMMUNICATION RIGHTS IN THE DIGITAL ERA

THE BEIJING PLATFORM FOR ACTION 30 YEARS ON

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

2025 | LISBON, PORTUGAL

CICANT

Fundação
para a Ciência
e a Tecnologia

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TECHNICAL SHEET

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Graphic Design | Ana Marta M. Flores

Logo Design | Nathalia Rech

Contact | WomComRights25@fcsh.unl.pt

womcomrights25.fcsh.unl.pt

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A CALL TO ANGER: A FEMINIST PARTICIPATORY APPROACH TO ANTI-TRAFFICKING COMMUNICATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE

Margarida Teixeira (Independent/Malmö University)

This article is a summary of a thesis developed in the context of Malmö University's Master of Communication for Development, which focused on analyzing why the voices of women affected by trafficking in human beings for sexual exploitation (THBSE) are often marginalized and why they are not usually included in the design and implementation of anti-trafficking campaigns. Although these campaigns present themselves as Communication for Social Change, the final result often betrays the principles of this form of communication. This article aims to tackle that gap, in partnership with the Serbian NGO Atina and their Youth Advocacy Group. The objective is to understand what is the perspective of women affected by THBSE in regards to institutional imagery of anti-trafficking campaigns and its persuasive potential for social change. The methodology was informed by a feminist participatory approach which included a) a focus group where participants were shown examples of anti-trafficking imagery, b) a workshop where participants designed their own campaign, and c) two expert interviews.

After analyzing a sample of 21 images of anti-trafficking campaigns from 12 countries (Serbia, USA, Canada, France, Spain, Portugal, Romania, Brazil, Luxembourg, Colombia, Ukraine and Israel), this thesis finds that anti-trafficking campaigns tend to fail at their potential for social change. This is due to misrepresentations that ignore the complexity of THBSE as a system of exploitation and by perpetuating harmful stereotypes about what a victim should or should not look like, thereby contributing to the silencing and marginalization of victims. Anti-trafficking campaigns also tend to rely on awareness-raising rather than promoting social change.

A VINDICATION OF THE RIGHTS OF WOMEN JOURNALISTS: ONLINE HARASSMENT THROUGH A HUMAN RIGHTS LENS

Susana Sampaio-Dias (University of Portsmouth), Maria João Silveirinha (ICNOVA) and João Miranda (Universidade de Coimbra).

Social media and digital journalism have shortened the proximity between journalists and audiences, heightening the risk of exposure to different forms of violent rhetoric, trolling and abuse, with physical, psychological, and professional consequences. Along with an understanding of the challenges this poses to media freedom and democracy, there is a growing awareness that women journalists are at the epicentre of risk. Both as women and as journalists, they are subjected to sexist comments and sexual violence threats as well as different shaming tactics, threats of physical violence, rape, kidnapping, doxing and racist, sexist, and misogynistic abuse. Following a decade of work on the safety of journalists, the UN Human Rights Council (2022), for example, recognised that 'online attacks against women journalists, including through targeted unlawful or arbitrary digital surveillance, are one of the serious contemporary threats to their safety' and 'condemns unequivocally the specific attacks on women journalists and media workers in relation to their work, such as gender-based discrimination, sexual and gender-based violence, threats, intimidation and harassment, online and offline' (Idem). Yet, despite these significant advances, and while acknowledging the gender disparity of online violence, there is still much to accomplish in establishing efficient accountability systems and preventing impunity for individuals who target journalists for their work and gender. In this presentation, we examine these issues as human rights violations, and inspired by the title of one of Mary Wollstonecraft's books, we vindicate the rights of women journalists. To this end, we explore how the protection and application of human rights legislation for women journalists in online contexts is

consequently affected, namely in the scope of their rights and the corresponding obligations from various actors, including states, platforms, and news organisations. We view the role of regulation mechanisms. Finally, we highlight the main issues emerging from the need to protect journalists in ways that consider women's challenges when they do not work in a safe environment.

AFRAID OF THE FUTURE

Carmen Beatriz Fernandez (DataStrategia) and Jenifer Campos (IESA).

In Latin America, the pandemic highlighted gender disparities in labor dynamics and digital opportunities. Our study analyzes data from three waves of the Latinobarómetro survey (pre-, during, and post-pandemic) across 17 countries to assess gender-specific effects. Women consistently reported higher perceptions of poverty and unemployment risk than men.

A Digital Dexterity Index (DDI), combining variables like social network use and education level, revealed that while both genders improved their digital skills during the pandemic, women demonstrated consistently higher digital dexterity. However, this advantage did not translate into greater confidence in the labor market. Women expressed heightened fear about their future employment prospects, despite their digital competence.

Our findings underscore a paradox: women's superior digital skills coexist with greater anxiety about their labor market future, reflecting persistent structural and psychological barriers. This research highlights the need for targeted policies to address gendered disparities in digital and labor market outcomes.

BEHIND THE HEADLINES: THE NARRATIVES OF WOMEN JOURNALISTS IN PURSUIT OF NEWS AND EQUALITY IN TURKEY

Burcu Şenel Alpuğan (Dr. - Lecturer, Hacettepe University Faculty of Communication, Ankara), Hakan Soner Şener (PhD Student, Hacettepe University Faculty of Communication, Ankara) and Burcu Şimşek (Associate Professor, Hacettepe University Faculty of Communication, Ankara).

The news media industry in Turkey is a male-dominated space, just like many other parts of the world, where women journalists come across systematic discrimination and unequal conditions. Addressing this gender gap and inequalities, this paper focuses on the narratives of women journalists living and working in Turkey. The data is based on the digital storytelling workshop entitled "Women in Pursuit of News and Equality" conducted with six participants including women journalists in April 2024 in Ankara, Turkey as part of the "Strong Civic Space for Gender Equality" project implemented by UN Women Turkey. The workshop enabled the participants to come together in a collective atmosphere first in the story circle and share their experiences of being women journalists in Turkey, followed by producing their digital stories which are 2-minute videos composed of their voiceover and visuals, reflecting their peculiar but intersecting experiences in different spheres of journalism ranging from streets to newsrooms, from media management to decision-making processes. Focusing on these digital stories, this paper aims to discuss that the oppression and discrimination that women journalists are subjected to in the media sector are not a personal matter, but are systematically created and legitimized due to patriarchal views and practices by various dynamics. In conclusion, while promoting the circulation of women journalists' narratives, this paper will contribute to exploring how a more inclusive and fairer news media environment depending on gender equality can be obtained by encouraging young women journalists to embrace the possibilities of solidarity, feel empowered, and be encouraged to pursue their goals.

BEYOND BINARIES: DETERMINANTS AND IMPEDIMENTS OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION AMONG TRANSGENDER INDIVIDUALS IN DELHI-NCR, INDIA

Rameez Raja (Aligarh Muslim University) and Prof Mohd Azam Khan (Aligarh Muslim University).

Financial inclusion is essential for the dignity, security, and self-reliance of marginalized communities, particularly the transgender population. Despite growing interest in financial accessibility, studies focusing on the determinants and barriers of financial inclusion for transgender individuals remain limited. This study surveyed 335 transgender participants in Delhi-NCR, India, using a purposive sampling technique. Data were analyzed with descriptive statistics and a probit model to identify key factors influencing financial inclusion. Results reveal that 60% of respondents possess formal accounts, but engagement with formal savings (45%) and credit (4.2%) remains limited. Education and income significantly enhance financial inclusion, with tertiary education and higher income levels positively influencing all indicators. Conversely, participation in survival economies, such as sex work and begging, emerges as a critical impediment, reducing the likelihood of financial inclusion by up to 40%. Barriers such as lack of documentation, I.D. discrepancies (52.5%), and discrimination (17.6%) further hinder access. The study underscores the potential of digital financial inclusion to mitigate these challenges, though adoption remains constrained by generational effects and systemic barriers. Policy recommendations include simplifying documentation, promoting financial literacy, addressing discrimination, and creating dignified employment opportunities to reduce reliance on survival economies.

BREAKING THE GENDERED MEDIA DISCOURSES: CHALLENGING FEMALE UNDERREPRESENTATION AND GENDER DISPARITIES IN SLOVENIAN MEDIA

Alenka Jelen (University of Stirling), Samo Kropivnik (University of Ljubljana) and Mateja Malnar Štembal (Ona Ve).

This research examines inequalities in gender representations in the media and proposes a plan for action in the under researched neoliberal postfeminist Slovenian environment. In collaboration between universities and a leading Slovenian NGO for gender equality, we conducted quantitative content and discourse analyses of 589 daily news published in the mainstream media between 15-21 May 2023 and their 1,210 sources according to their gender, role, expertise, theme, and stereotypical representations. The results demonstrate an overwhelming 73% male domination in news sources with women being underrepresented in all categories, from elite and expert sources (particularly in politics and economy) to ordinary citizens, and in all themes of media reporting, including “feminised” issues (other gender identities were not detected in the sample). Men have notably higher credibility, competency, authority, rationality and media influence in comparison with their “emotional” and “caring” female counterparts. These media representations reinforce gender biases, stereotypes, and inequalities in Slovenian society, marginalising women and discouraging their media presence, exacerbated by gender-based violence online and offline.

The results align with Slovenian, European, and global media studies, including GMMP, echoing urgent calls for gender mainstreaming to enhance gender equality, diversity, and inclusion in the media and policies (including the Slovenian Media Act and Code of Ethics for Journalists).

To this end, we have designed a plan for action and delivered early interventions, involving: (1) partnerships with media organisations and signing commitments 50:50; (2) media workshops raising awareness of gender inequalities in media discourses and their implications for human rights, democratic participation, societal understandings of gender, media ratings and revenues; (3) awareness-raising advocacy campaigns on gender inequalities in the media; and (4) mentorship

programmes empowering women to participate in the media. Repeat research is planned in May 2025 to monitor changes in media gender representations in the aftermath of these interventions.

BREAKING THROUGH AS THE 'OTHER': PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCES OF WOMEN JOURNALISTS FROM MINORITY COMMUNITIES

Einat Lachover (Sapir Academic College)

Media organizations globally are grappling with workforce diversity, and Israeli news organizations reflect broader patterns of structural inequalities and representation. This study adopts a "bottom-up" perspective to examine the lived experiences of individuals from marginalized groups within mainstream Hebrew news organizations, specifically focusing on the intersectional challenges faced by women journalists from minority communities. This research investigates how national and ethnic minority professionals navigate systemic barriers while maintaining their agency within dominant media institutions. This study argues that workforce diversity in news-making is fundamental to transforming institutional culture and practices. Through an intersectional lens, this presentation will analyze the complex subjectivities of Israeli women journalists from two distinct minority groups working in mainstream television, radio, and digital newsrooms. It examines both the structural barriers they face and their strategies for resilience in an environment characterized by tokenistic "diversity management" approaches. The research focuses on two systematically marginalized groups: (1) Ethiopian Jewish women journalists, who face discrimination based on racial prejudice and are often patronized due to their immigrant background; (2) Palestinian women journalists living in Israel, who experience multiple layers of discrimination as non-Jewish citizens, affecting their socioeconomic, civil, and political rights. Methodologically, this study employs a phenomenological approach, drawing on narrative interviews with 22 women journalists. Using grounded theory and thematic analysis, the research explores key themes including: • The paradoxical advantage of "otherness" in entering the profession • The personal and professional costs of tokenism and associated coping strategies • Temporal shifts in token status • Community-related dilemmas stemming from their professional position

This research contributes to gender and intersectional studies in media production by examining how tokenism and structural inequalities affect women journalists from minority groups, revealing both the systemic barriers they encounter and the strategies they employ to navigate and challenge these constraints in the process of cultural production.

COMMUNICATING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE AT BEIRA INTERIOR/PORTUGAL: HOW AND WHERE IS IT DISSEMINATED

Catarina Sales (UBI and Cies_Iscte) and Haphisa Mugnaini (UBI and UFMA).

Gender-based violence against women is a persistent problem worldwide and Portugal is no exception. This communication is about an ongoing project named AUDIAM (Audioteca de Apoio à Mulher: hyperaudio como recurso educacional de enfrentamento à violência contra mulher/ Audio library to support women: hyperaudio as an educational and communication resource to fight violence against women). It consists in a partnership between the University of Beira Interior (Portugal) and the Federal University of Maranhão (Brazil) aiming to discuss processes of violence against women through a parallel analysis between the two countries. It focus media production on this topic as a privileged space for shaping public opinion. Considering the sociocultural and demographic specificities of Beira Interior region/Portugal, namely the indicators of violence (INE, 2024) and the existence of a strong regional media (Correia, 2011), the Portuguese team investigated the incidence of gender violence in this region in Portugal, based on its presence in the Portuguese media in

comparison with the official cases registered. Preliminary data from the data collection carried out in the second half of 2024 reveals low coverage of crimes against women in this region, where only physical violence in the domestic context was considered, ignoring other forms of abuse, such as psychological and economic violence. This type of crime is rarely publicised in the region creating the false impression that it is a type of crime that does not occur in the region. The conclusion is that there is a discrepancy between gender based official data and the data disseminated by media - both national and local. The authors believe that this research can bring a relevant contribution to the WOMCOMRIGHTS 25 event, namely in the Gender and intersectional issues in media production topic.

CONFRONTING DIGITAL GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE: FEMINIST PERSPECTIVES ON MEDIA POLICIES AND PLATFORM DESIGN

Mariacristina Sciannamblo (Sapienza University of Rome), Chiara Carbone (University of Padua), Francesca Comunello (Sapienza University of Rome), Cosimo Marco Scarcelli (University of Padua), Lorenza Parisi (Sapienza University of Rome) and Fabrizio Di Buono (Sapienza University of Rome).

Digital media platforms have not only facilitated gender-based violence but have also failed to effectively address misogyny and protect women's digital rights, disproportionately affecting marginalized groups facing multiple forms of discrimination, such as racism, ableism, LGBTQ+phobia, and classism. While these platforms reinforce hegemonic relational models, they also hold the potential to foster fairer and more democratic digital spaces. This contribution, grounded in a techno-feminist perspective (Wajcman 2007; Åsberg, Lykke 2010), explores the intersection of digital design, media policies, and broader socio-technical politics in shaping online environments. Addressing digital gender-based violence effectively (Henry et al., 2020) requires feminist and intersectional approaches that critically interrogate the structures and functioning of digital technologies – including programming languages, aesthetics, media policies, and gendered affordances (Schwartz, Neff 2019). This is crucial because algorithmic resistance (Bonini, Tréré 2024) and any response to digital harassment and gender-based violence become possible only through an in-depth critique of digital infrastructures themselves, emphasizing the need to redesign technologies in ways that challenge systemic biases rather than perpetuate them. We present preliminary findings from four focus groups conducted in Italy as part of a nationwide research project. The project investigates how digital technologies enable new and reinforce old forms of abuse and explores collective strategies of resilience, resistance, and self-determination developed by users (Bucher, Helmond 2017). More specifically, the focus groups examine the role of design, policies and the forms of response to gender-based violence online by engaging activists, anti-violence workers, policy-makers, and designers. By integrating feminist and intersectional perspectives, this work contributes to ongoing discussions on media policy, digital harassment, and strategies for ensuring a more equitable digital future.

CYBERVICTIMISATION OF LGBTQ+: CURRENT STATE IN SWITZERLAND

Cristina Cretu-Adatte (Institute of economic crime investigation) and Estelle Bulliard (Institute of economic crime investigation).

In a context of rising anti-LGBTIQ+ violence worldwide, this study explores the cybervictimisation of LGBTQ+ individuals in Switzerland. Addressing critical knowledge gaps, the research aims to identify digital abuse patterns, risk and protective factors, and coping strategies used by targets and victims.

Using a qualitative methodology, the research team conducted 20 interviews with professionals from LGBTIQ+ associations, research institutes, governmental agencies, and legal representatives, followed by 18 interviews with LGBTIQ+ individuals who have experienced online victimization. Findings highlight both general and LGBTIQ+-specific cyberviolence, including outing, targeted cyber raids, and sextortion. Key risk factors include online exposure, socio-demographic vulnerabilities, and lack of social support, while protective factors involve community solidarity, digital self-management, and institutional assistance. The communication underscores the challenges of legal responses due to anonymity and enforcement gaps, as well as victims' reluctance to engage with law enforcement. Furthermore, it reveals how online platforms, particularly social media and dating apps, amplify risks due to insufficient moderation. The findings provide insights for policymakers, digital platforms, and advocacy groups to improve online safety measures for LGBTIQ+ individuals.

DIGITAL INTRUSIONS AND RESISTANCE: ITALIAN TEENAGERS' EXPERIENCES OF ONLINE GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

Vittoria Bernardini (University of Padova), Raffaella Maiullo (Sapienza University of Rome), Cosimo Marco Scarcelli (University of Padova), Lorenza Parisi (Sapienza University of Rome) and Francesca Comunello (Sapienza University of Rome).

The use of digital media by young people in relation to intimate relationships and practices has received increasing attention, often framed in a sensationalized manner, which over-simplifies the debate on media usage to a focus on its effects, often at the expense of young women (Bragg & Buckingham, 2009; Tiidenberg & van der Nagel, 2020). Moving beyond a media effects approach, sociocultural digital research has addressed gender and intimacy by adopting a mutual shaping perspective to explore the interactions between digital media and gender (Van Zoonen, 2002). This approach seeks to understand how the social meaning of digital media is shaped by prevailing gender conceptions (Wajcman, 1991).

This paper analyses how Italian teenagers (aged 16–18) (re)define their understanding of gender and intimacy through their engagement with digital media in their daily lives. Six focus groups and around 60 individual semi-structured interviews were carried out in different Italian cities. Using a participatory design approach, each research instrument is co-constructed with a group of 10 teenagers. The analysis of the empirical material involves qualitative thematic analysis (focus groups and interviews) and statistical analysis of survey data.

The findings from focus groups and interviews encompass a broad range of digital practices in connection with gender and intimacy. This paper focuses on teenagers' experiences of gender-based violence, including digital dating abuse and image-based sexual harassment and abuse. Results evidence how teenage girls experience offline and online forms of gender-based violence, which occur in a context of heteronormative and gendered scripts. In particular, men's and boys' digital "intrusions" into girls' lives on social media appear normalized (Meehan, 2022) and have negative impacts on their well-being and relationships. However, girls also adopt complex strategies to navigate digital media safely.

DIGITALIZED COUNTERNARRATION OF WOMEN DURING THE LAST ARGENTINIAN DICTATORSHIP (1976–1983). HERSTORIES FOR A COLLECTIVE COUNTERMEMORY.

Martina Ailén García (UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA).

The speech pronounced by the incumbent Argentinian President, Javier Milei, in the most recent World Economic Forum, serves as a terrifying alert of the potential legal regressions in terms of gender equality, achieved so far with so much effort by the Argentinian feminist movement.

Adopting a feminist perspective, and employing ethnographic and sociological approaches, this contribution intends to examine not only the role of women's emotions during an ultraright-wing government but also how recognizing political commitment of digitalized countermemories is crucial to understand women's agency during the last Argentinian dictatorship (1976-1983). Indeed, this paper aims to give visibility to the importance of women's rights of expression about the discrimination and violence militant women have suffered.

This study seeks to reinterpret the violation of Human and Women's Rights within a repressive context, following some feminist theoretical frameworks, such as Ahmed's Affective Politics of Fear, Caruth's notion of ethical responsibility and legitimization of witness, and the concept of post-memory by Hannah Arendt. Moreover, it refers to the theories offered by Argentinian scholars, such as Álvarez, Bacci, Felitti, and Sutton who highlight the relevance of women's voices to testify and counternarrate the official Argentinian history, using feelings as a valid key to read the past.

Thus, considering emotions as epistemic and interpretative resources, the article analyzes selected digitalized women's memories and multimedia material used to spread consciousness on gendered and stereotyped historical narration, like the revictimization and shame women feel while denouncing sexual violences.

The ambitious goal is to encourage intergenerational and intercontinental dialogue between the Global South and the Global North to remind the world that women's rights cannot never be taken for granted. Only through international awareness and empathetic collaboration can the perpetration of the patriarchal victimization and underrepresentation of women in historical, social, educational, political and digital contexts be avoided.

DISCURSIVE WEAPONISATION OF THE CONCEPT OF TRUTH AND SOCIAL MEDIA POLICIES OF META: NEWS COVERAGE AND POLICY ANALYSIS FROM A FEMINIST STANDPOINT

Dilara Asardag (Tampere University).

In an Instagram video, Meta CEO Mark Zuckerberg has recently announced that there will be major changes to his company's content moderation policies that he identified as an effort to "get back to our roots and focus on reducing mistakes, simplifying our policies and restoring free expression". Similar to the so-called "free speech absolutist" Elon Musk, according to Zuckerberg, the main impetus for change is "blocking censorship", "the desire to bolster free expression" and retreating from efforts to diminish the spread of what he calls hate speech (2025). However, under conditions of rising anti-gender backlash transnationally (see. US and Turkey, for example; Abaday, 2024), these changes are deeply concerning for social media researchers, gender studies researchers and relevant activism/advocacy networks as well. As the concept of truth is being weaponised by right wing politicians and CEOs, it is hypothesised that these implied policy moves of META are significantly geared towards right-wing pundits like president-elect Trump and other conservatives, as they are now allowed spreading more lies, hate speech, and conspiracy theories as facts, camouflaged as free expression. Therefore, in this research, we attempt to understand (i) how are the proposed policy changes discursively constructed in major European online news outlets; (ii) what are the actual policy changes, taking into account women and LGBTIQ+ identities? In order to answer these questions, 10 online news articles as well as META's policy documents will be analysed through the method of document analysis. In this article, feminist standpoint theory and strong objectivity (Harding, 1986;

Hartsock, 1983) will be utilised as a theoretical framework. We believe that the findings of this research study will make a valuable contribution to Women's Communication Rights in the Digital Era: the Beijing Platform for Action 30 Years on Conference. This paper is expected to have great progress by the time of the mentioned conference.

FORMS OF REAPPROPRIATION IN RESPONSE TO GENDER BIASES IN THE NETWORK: AN APPROACH TO THE CREATIVE DOCUMENTARY OF MARÍA CAÑAS AND FLORENCIA ALIBERTI.

Ariadna Moreno Pellejero (Temporary lecturer).

Social networks and web platforms consist of words, images, videos, tags, hashtags, emoticons and hyperlinks. Content is suggested to us according to what we click on, what we "like" or comment on, leaving our digital footprint. The algorithm in turn is associated with gender biases that replicate our ways of interacting on the network based on the data we provide, in addition to reflecting the underrepresentation of women in the design and production of artificial intelligences (Castaneda et al., 2022). As an alternative that tries to confront these biases and powers, movements and publications such as Data Feminism or Design Justice, manifestos such as Xenophemist, or projects such as Feminist Data Set emerge, rising questions about the gender biases in Machine Learning systems and claiming the need to create a new creative language that counteracts the gender constructions that predominate in Internet culture, generating new spaces for artistic experimentation (Costanza-Chock, 2020; D'Ignazio & Klein, 2023; Sinderson, 2017, 2020; Hester, 2018; Laboria Cuboniks, 2014). At the same time, female directors and artists who use new media in a creative way to show our contemporaneity are emerging. Here I will analyze the work of the Sevillian María Cañas Padre no nuestro (2019) and the documentary series (Auto)exposiciones (2012-2015) by the Argentinean, between Barcelona and Paris, Florencia Aliberti. Two authors who invite, through the reappropriation of the archive, to a reflection on the ways in which we relate to each other and on the gender connotations implied by the daily rituals we reiterate. To address all this, I will base on texts from Film and Media Studies (Costanza-Chock, 2020; Russell, 1999; Vannini, 2023), Spectatoriality and Gender Studies (Marks, 2000, 2024; Sobchack, 1992, 2004), and Digital Culture (Guardiola, 2018; Hester, 2018; Remedios, 2010; Zafra, 2013) with an interdisciplinary approach.

FROM MYTHOLOGY TO TECHNOLOGY: GENDER IN AI AND THE ELIZA EFFECT

Arzu Bayar (Ankara University).

The connection of mythology with technology, and the past with present and future, is particularly significant for the reproduction of gender norms. The design of AI-powered humanoid robots as female figures can be interpreted as a continuation of gendered representations stretching from ancient Greece to the present. In the Pygmalion myth, the male artist creates an ideal female figure according to his desires and prays to the gods to bring her to life. Today, engineers, coders, and designers engage in a similar act of creation by producing female looking robots. Robots like Sophia, Ai-Da, and Erica are not merely technical objects; they also serve as reflections and reinforcements of gender perceptions in a male-dominated society. This article critically examines how the Pygmalion myth emerges in contemporary technology through the lens of feminism. A significant early example of this phenomenon is Joseph Weizenbaum's Eliza, the world's first chatbot, which simulated a psychotherapist but was perceived by users as an empathetic female presence. Much like Pygmalion's Galatea, Eliza was not only programmed but also equipped with human expectations, revealing how gendered assumptions shape interactions with AI. Why do female looking robots receive more media

attention compared to their male counterparts? How does their association with empathy, service, and aesthetic production contribute to the reinforcement of gender norms? What is the connection between algorithmic governmentality and the historical domination over the female body and labor? The methodology involves a detailed critical analysis of case studies such as Eliza, Sophia and Ai-Da, focusing on visual, discursive, and cultural codes to deconstruct the gendered representations of AI robots. Drawing from critical feminism and technology studies, this analysis seeks to reveal how gender hierarchies are embedded in artificial intelligence. Ultimately, this paper argues that AI robots are not merely technical objects but rather tools that sustain cultural structures.

GENDER EQUALITY IN THE DIGITAL TRANSITION IN PORTUGAL: WHAT PLACE FOR WOMEN?

Rosa Monteiro (FEUC), Lina Coelho (FEUC - CES), Luísa Ribeiro Lopes (ISCSP), Margarida Vasconcelos (FPUL) and Mariana Santos (FEUC-CES).

Despite the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) sector's significance for digital transformation, women still account for only 22% of the workforce - a gap that not only limits their opportunities but also hinders an inclusive, equitable digital transition. This communication will present the preliminary findings of the Women4Digital: a project aiming to better understand, characterize and monitor public policies designed to promote women's participation and address horizontal segregation in Portugal's ICT sector since 2017. Our research adopts a mixed-method approach, combining document analysis, interviews, and stakeholder focus groups, to map the diversity of policies and instruments implemented at the national level. These include initiatives such as the "Engineers for a Day" program and the integration of gender equality goals in the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030, and the Action Plan for Digital Transition, as well as INCoDe.2030. Our preliminary findings highlight both progress in raising awareness and fostering collaboration across government, education, and the private sector, as well as persistent challenges, such as inconsistent application of gender mainstreaming principles, lack of robust monitoring tools, and insufficient integration of gender perspectives in broader policy frameworks. This presentation will contribute to the conference discussion by examining how national efforts align with international frameworks, including the European Gender Equality Strategy and the Digital Compass for the Digital Decade. It will also propose practical recommendations for enhancing policy design, implementation, and evaluation, emphasizing the importance of systemic and intersectional approaches to overcoming structural barriers. By shedding light on current successes and shortcomings, we aim to advance dialogue on fostering a more inclusive digital transition that empowers women and reduces gender disparities in the ICT sector.

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENTS: TOWARDS THE NORMALIZATION OF ONLINE ABUSE AND HARASSMENT AGAINST WOMEN?

Uxia Carral (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid) and Clara Sainz de Baranda Andujar (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid).

Although Section J of the Beijing Platform for Action promotes a balanced and non-stereotyped representation of women in the media, dynamics of gender-based violence persist in digital environments and have intensified with the expansion of online platforms. Gender-based harassment and abuse in the digital sphere have become widespread phenomena, where misogyny and other forms of intersectional discrimination are reproduced and amplified, reinforcing the exclusion and victimization of women in online environments.

In this context, the present study aims to conduct an in-depth analysis of perceptions regarding gender-based violence in digital environments, with a particular focus on levels of awareness, prevailing attitudes, the most common formats and spaces where such violence occurs, and opinions on the responsibilities of both users and digital platforms. To this end, a survey was conducted in current 2025 with a sample of 1,000 individuals residing in Spain, selected based on diverse sociodemographic profiles. In order to provide a comprehensive analysis of the issue, the study incorporates an intersectional perspective that considers variables such as age, socioeconomic status, educational level, and sexual orientation.

Preliminary results reveal significant differences in the perception of digital gender-based violence, highlighting a greater awareness of the issue among women compared to men. Furthermore, individuals belonging to vulnerable groups report more intense experiences of online harassment due to the convergence of various forms of intersectional discrimination. Another relevant finding is the tendency to normalize certain manifestations of digital violence, even when their prevalence is high— a phenomenon that may be partly attributed to their occurrence in more private virtual spaces.

In sum, this study provides a multidimensional perspective on the persistence and normalization of digital harassment and violence against women, offering evidence that will contribute to the development of strategies aimed at fostering safer, more equitable and inclusive digital environments.

GENDERED PERCEPTIONS AND DIGITAL HARASSMENT IN TIKTOK SCIENCE COMMUNICATION: INSIGHTS FROM THE GERMAN ENERGY TRANSITION DEBATE

Eva-Maria Grommes (University of Applied Sciences Cologne), Anne Maren Feldhof (University of Applied Sciences Cologne) and Tara Marie Schindler (University of Applied Sciences Cologne).

Social media platforms such as TikTok have transformed science communication, providing accessible spaces for discourse and reaching diverse stakeholder groups while cultivating polarisation. This study examines the role of gender, perceived authenticity, as well as digital harassment and misogyny in science communication about the German energy transition on TikTok. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research combines qualitative content analysis of polarising comments on TikTok videos from the German TikTok channel @energiewende.erklaert, including interviews conducted with commenters, content creators, and science communicators. These methods allow a detailed examination of how gender-specific prejudices and dynamics influence interactions and perceptions in digital spaces. This paper hypothesises that scientists perceived as female are more likely to have their content dismissed as subjective and lacking expertise, whereas scientists perceived as male are more frequently seen as objective and credible. While prior research, such as Knobloch-Westerwick et al. (2013), has investigated gender biases in perceived scientific quality, this paper extends such findings to TikTok—a platform increasingly shaping public scientific engagement. These perceptions reflect societal norms that privilege objectivity as a scientific ideal, while systematically marginalising female perspectives by rejecting them as subjective, irrespective of the quality of their contributions (Paulitz, 2019). The study also examines patterns of stigmatisation and objectification faced by female-perceived creators, researching whether these dynamics are evident in TikTok-based science communication in Germany. By adopting a feminist framework, the research contributes to understanding barriers to recognising expertise and how societal norms create digital spaces of exclusion. Additionally, it offers key insights into gendered barriers in the perception of scientific expertise and highlights the role of digital harassment in shaping these dynamics. By addressing gendered barriers in perceptions of expertise, this work not only advances academic understanding but also offers practical strategies to foster more inclusive and equitable digital environments for science communication.

HJABOPHOBIA IN MOROCCAN NEWSROOMS: NAVIGATING IDENTITY, REPRESENTATION, AND RESISTANCE

Basma Wajih (university of Oviedo).

Despite Morocco's being an Islamic country with a diverse news landscape, journalists who wear the hijab often face systemic exclusion, particularly in visual news. According to Hawzah News Agency (2016), hijabi journalists are nearly invisible on Moroccan television, raising concerns about structural discrimination in media. This article explores hijabophobia within Moroccan newsrooms, focusing on the professional experiences of hijabi journalists. Grounded in decolonial feminism and intersectionality, this research critically examines how gendered biases and colonial legacies shape newsroom cultures. Indeed, I employed semi-structured interviews with 15 hijabi journalists across various Moroccan news outlets working in different positions and I was able to investigate their career trajectories, professional challenges, and coping mechanisms within predominantly male-dominated newsroom spaces. Thematic analysis is used to identify recurring patterns in their experiences, revealing the intersectional barriers they encounter in accessing decision-making positions and shaping media narratives. The research findings indicate that journalists who wear hijabs often find themselves sidelined from on-camera positions, which restricts their visibility and influence in the industry. Also, they face constrained opportunities for career advancement, which makes it difficult to climb the professional ladder. Implicit pressures also exist, compelling them to adhere to the prevailing secular norms dominating newsroom culture. Additionally, they are frequently pigeonholed into creating content specifically related to Islamic programs, which limits the scope of their contributions and minimizes their representation in broader discussions in the news. In conclusion, this study underscores the enduring influence of colonial legacies on contemporary practices within newsrooms, revealing how these historical dynamics contribute to the systematic exclusion of hijabi journalists, ultimately perpetuating systemic barriers to inclusion within the news landscape, thereby hindering the progress towards a diverse and representative journalism industry.

MEDIA CONSUMPTION AND AGEING: DIVERSITY AND COMPLEXITY IN WOMEN'S EXPERIENCES

Elizângela Noronha (Universidade Católica Portuguesa/CECC).

The global population is ageing like never before in history. According to data from the World Population Ageing 2020 – Highlights report (UN), the proportion of people aged 65 or older is expected to increase from 9.3% in 2020 to approximately 16.0% by 2050. Beyond this document, there is extensive research across various fields documenting that this ageing population also has a predominant gender: female. On average, women live longer and make up the majority of older people. A significant female majority is found when visiting care homes, day centres, and households for the application of an exploratory questionnaire, which is part of broader research aimed at characterising the media consumption habits of people aged 65 or older residing in the municipality of Covilhã. In addition to representing 72% of the 355 individuals who responded to the survey, women also revealed a diversity of experiences and life stories that challenge age and gender stereotypes. Using an audience anthropology approach (Morley & Silverstone, 2002) that recognises the social production of meaning by the audience, we identified, through both quantitative and qualitative data, that women have less interest in soap operas than men, and nearly half of the female respondents watch sports programmes, particularly when it comes to the Portuguese national team, Benfica, or Sporting. We also found older women who prefer quiet over television noise, as well as women who rely on television or video calls with distant family members as a means of combating loneliness. The

mediated religious practices and the use of communication and information technologies, such as computers and digital social networks, identified and recorded during the fieldwork, also revealed varying uses and experiences among the respondents. In this presentation, we will provide insights that demonstrate the diversity and complexity of ageing in general, and particularly among women.

NEGOTIATING PLATFORMISED (IN)VISIBILITY: EXPLORING AMBIVALENT PERCEPTIONS OF VISIBILITY IN FEMINIST USES OF INSTAGRAM STORIES

Sofia P. Caldeira (CICANT, Lusófona University).

Digital and social media have long been used for feminist and activist purposes (Marwick, 2019), contributing to the increased popular visibility of the movement in the last decade (Banet-Weiser, 2018). Social media platforms facilitate practices of visibility politics (Whittier, 2017), increasing public exposure for social justice issues and marginalised groups or identities. In this context, platformised visibility has often been framed in a positive light. However, visibility can be unequally distributed and even carry risks when extended to unintended or hostile audiences (Jiménez-Martínez and Edwards, 2023; Stegeman et al., 2024), particularly in a climate of growing anti-feminist pushback and backlash. This communication explores ambivalent perceptions and relationships with the notion of platformised (in)visibility. Recognising that particular social media platforms and features can facilitate specific modes of feminist expression (Barbala, 2022b; Keller, 2019), this paper engages with Instagram users who share feminist or social justice content via Instagram Stories. The paper draws on 18 semi-structured interviews conducted in the Portuguese context. Participants, ages 20–50, have different feminist profiles, and use Instagram for different purposes – personal, professional, activist, or a combination of them. Interviews were conducted between June and August 2023, via Zoom, and lasted on average 1 hour. With the consent of participants, the interviews were recorded, transcribed verbatim, and thematically coded using MaxQDA. This communication foregrounds the paradoxical space that Instagram Stories occupies in the imagined attention economy of the platform. On one hand, Stories are framed as a tool for strategically increasing and sustaining feminist algorithmic visibility. Stories' communicative affordances are seen as fostering feelings of interconnectedness and grounding feminist community-building. On the other hand, the interviews also highlight how unintended visibility can open one's Instagram to backlash. In this context, Stories are paradoxically imagined as enabling circumscribed forms of circulation among more restricted and like-minded audiences – a feminist bubble that sustains safer digital spaces. Recognising the impacts of the labour necessary to achieve and maintain platformised visibility, deliberate reductions in platformised visibility – through strategies of partial or temporary disengagement from social media – are also explored as potential practices of feminist self-care.

"NEVER TO OLD TO PROTEST....": DIGITAL ACTIVISM OF "GRANNIES AGAINST THE RIGHT"

Ricarda Drueeke (University of Salzburg).

Founded on Facebook in 2017, "Grannies Against the Right" (Omas gegen Rechts) is an Austrian grassroots movement of mostly elderly women protesting against right-wing extremism and advocating for justice at any age. The group leverages digital platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and X for networking and mobilization, while street protests remain their primary form of action. This dual strategy demonstrates how activism can navigate the intersections of online and offline spaces to address pressing social and political issues. This study addresses two questions: (1) How do the Grannies utilize digital media for their activism? (2) How do these digital articulations of protest

shape the formation of publics? Building on theories of public spheres and participatory cultures, the analysis emphasizes how digital and physical interactions create counter-publics that challenge hegemonic discourses. Public spheres, increasingly interconnected through digital media, play a central role in contemporary activism by offering spaces for collective discourse and critique (Kaun et al., 2016). Media practices act as tools for transformation, amplifying marginalized voices and enabling diverse perspectives to influence public discourse (Mattoni, 2017). Methodologically, the study employs a digital ethnographic approach and qualitative content analysis. Over three months in 2024, the group's activities on Instagram, X, and TikTok were observed and analyzed, with further data collection planned for 2025. Textual and visual content analysis identified forms of agency and the role of media in mobilization. Findings show that the Grannies strategically use different platforms for informing, mobilizing, and fostering participation. Visual symbols, such as self-knitted hats, reinforce their generational identity and collective ethos. Unlike event-based or hashtag activism, their sustained engagement ensures stability and impact over time. This study highlights the significance of hybrid strategies. By integrating digital and physical practices, "Grannies Against the Right" demonstrates how intergenerational activism can achieve visibility, agency, and lasting social change.

ONLINE ATTACKS AGAINST FEMINIST ACTIVISTS IN TURKEY: CHALLENGES AND COPING STRATEGIES

Gulum Sener Ulagay (15 November Cyprus University).

The rise of digital platforms has amplified the visibility of feminist activism, but it has also led to an increase in anti-feminist backlash. In Turkey, feminist activists navigate a digital landscape marked by gender-based violence, including trolling, digital lynching, and doxxing. Online harassment is driven by a variety of groups, including Islamist conservatives, nationalists, men's rights groups, government-aligned anti-feminist networks and media, and TERFs (trans-exclusionary radical feminists). These groups use digital platforms to mobilize support, conduct campaigns, and harass feminist activists, portraying them as enemies of the state, "threats to family values," and immoral influences eroding national and religious traditions. Such narratives aim to delegitimize feminist movements, exacerbate gender-based inequality, and foster societal polarization. Despite facing surveillance, organized online attacks, and systemic repression, feminist activists in Turkey continue to resist and mobilize for gender equality and social justice. Their strategies to tackle digital threats include enhancing digital security measures, advocating for broader societal change beyond virtual spaces, and relying on solidarity networks. Collective action fosters resilience and enables activists to address incidents collaboratively, limiting the psychological toll of digital harassment. This study examines the multifaceted nature of these online attacks, their asymmetrical impact on different feminist groups, and the coping mechanisms employed to mitigate their effects. It is based on in-depth interviews with feminist activists from diverse organizations in Turkey, offering insights into their lived experiences and strategies for navigating online violence. By highlighting these dynamics, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of the challenges of feminist activism in digital spaces and the resilience of feminist resistance.

ONLINE HATE SPEECH, GENDER, AND REGULATION: WHAT STRATEGIES SAFEGUARD WOMEN'S DIGITAL PARTICIPATION?

Rita Basílio Simões (University of Coimbra, Faculty of Arts and Humanities, Centre for Social Studies, Portugal).

This paper explores the intersections between freedom of expression, hate speech, and gender, with a particular focus on the impact of online misogyny on women politicians and journalists. Grounded in feminist media studies (e.g., Sobieraj, 2018; Richardson-Self, 2021; Cuklanz, 2023; Simões, 2024) and regulatory policy research (e.g., Citron & Norton, 2011; Klonick, 2018; Baker & Jurasz, 2019; de Silva, 2020), it closely aligns with key conference themes such as Gender and media regulation and Online gendered harassment and abuse. Empirically, this study draws on data collected from a research project on online violence and hate targeting women, including those in politics and journalism, conducted in Portugal between 2021 and 2022. The findings highlight the key dimensions of online misogyny and the significant challenges it poses — both locally and globally — to women’s participation in digital spaces and their freedom of expression. These issues are particularly relevant for women politicians and journalists, who must navigate increasingly hostile online environments. While mapping these challenges, the central question guiding this paper is how online hate speech targeting women can be effectively addressed. To this end, I examine legal frameworks alongside platform-based and user-driven regulatory approaches. Considerable efforts are being made to regulate online hate speech, as I will illustrate. However, a critical issue remains: to what extent do these regulatory measures incorporate an understanding of the power and gender dynamics that underpin structural misogyny? This paper seeks to contribute to this debate by arguing that regulation, in its various forms, must engage with the structural causes of hate speech against women to be truly effective in protecting users and fostering social change.

PERCEPTIONS FROM CENTENNIAL REGIONAL NEWSPAPER PROFESSIONALS ON THE REGIONAL PRESS FEMINISATION PROCESS

Liliana Carona (Instituto Politécnico da Guarda) and Rita Basílio Simões (Universidade de Coimbra).

In this study, we explore the feminization of newsrooms in Portuguese regional press, investigating the dominant socio-professional profiles and the distribution of management and leadership positions between men and women. Based on a sample of five newspapers, representative of a universe of 40 centenary regional titles in Portugal, 20 interviews were conducted with professionals from these newsrooms to identify potential gender inequalities. Using thematic critical analysis, we highlight how their narratives reveal obstacles and barriers that limit women's access to leadership roles within the journalistic hierarchy. By confirming the presence of the phenomenon known as "glass ceilings" in regional press newsrooms, this study contributes not only to understanding the role of gender in journalistic work practices but also to a deeper understanding of the composition of regional newsrooms, a sector that remains peripheral in research agendas. Within the theme of gender and intersectional issues in media production, it was possible to frame this study, which brings us back to old newsroom practices that are perpetuated in most cases today. In other words, the celebration of the 30th anniversary of the Beijing Platform for Action (BPfA) makes it clear that some of the strategic objectives remain unfulfilled, particularly in the paragraph that recalls the role of women in power and decision-making, in which ‘without the active participation of women and the incorporation of their perspectives at all levels of decision-making, the goals of equality, development and peace cannot be achieved, and peace cannot be achieved’. Women are still largely under-represented in managerial and leadership positions, as this document (BPfA) and this study continues to show.

PERFORMING PEASANTRY: FIELD NOTES ON SOCIAL MEDIA MEDIATED AUTHENTICITY PERFORMANCES OF RURAL WOMEN IN THRACE

Feride Güner (Mustafa Kemal University).

Between June and September 2022, I conducted a feminist digital media ethnography in several villages of Tekirdağ, located in the Thrace region of Western Turkey. Over three months of fieldwork, I sought to understand the meanings and roles that digital media assume in the daily lives of rural women. One of my key research questions was how digital media influence rural women's ability to question, transform, and reproduce their gender-based subordination. In this study, I aim to present a pattern that emerged as one of the most prevalent tendencies I observed in the ordinary rhythm of daily life during my fieldwork: how and why rural women engage in performances of peasantry and "authenticity" on social media. I explore how social media provide rural women with a symbolic and cultural space that enables them to construct their subjectivities and peasant identities in an interwoven manner. Data obtained through participant observation, in-depth interviews, and informal conversations reveal that rural women's social media-mediated performances of authenticity and peasantry manifest in three primary domains: women's labor and rural activities; social environment and relationships; and traditional and pastoral landscapes. In the villages where I conducted my research, many women resisted the "classic" peasant identity, arguing that the symbolic, class-based, physical, and spatial distinctions between rural and urban life were eroding. Simultaneously, however, the "classic" cultural fantasy of peasantry -its moral superiority, "naturalness," "purity," and the "innocent," tightly-knit, face-to-face community relations- was being romanticized. My observations indicate that social media played a crucial mediating role in constructing this cultural fantasy, revitalizing the supposedly fading "authentic village sociality," and performing it. While rural women reproduced certain normative, ideological, and cultural imaginaries of peasantry through digital media, they also challenged these very images. Ultimately, economic, social, and cultural transformations have altered the ways subjects position peasantry. However, digital transformation marks a new stage in which many practices previously considered "signifiers of peasantry" have become sources of pride. In this sense, I argue that digital media provide rural women with a significant portion of the symbolic materials and spaces they need to construct their cultural identities and subjectivities.

PORNIFIED ABUSE: AI-FACILITATED SEXUAL VIOLENCE

Maria João Faustino (CES-UC).

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) has brought severe implications for violence against women, by enabling the creation of "deepfakes": hyperrealistic synthetic media. Non-consensual sexual deepfakes constitute a form of image-based sexual abuse, along with other forms of production, dissemination or threat to disseminate intimate images (McGlynn and Rackley, 2017). Deepfake sexual abuse has grown exponentially in the last few years. The proliferation of undressing apps and websites makes this software easily accessible. In Portugal, there is still no research specifically focused on AI-facilitated sexual violence, its prevalence and its consequences. Despite the lack of statistical data, Linha Internet Segura (the Safer Internet Helpline) has reported an exponential increase in the reported cases of deepfake sexual abuse (Alves, 2023). In this presentation, I analyze how deepfake sexual abuse is represented in the Portuguese mediascape, by looking at the main newspapers and newsmagazines available online (i.e. Público; Expresso; Observador; Correio da Manhã; Visão; Sábado). I will unpack the discursive framings, looking at the terminology used and the gendered

meanings ascribed to it. I show that AI-facilitated sexual violence is mostly - and problematically - framed as fake pornography.

PRODUCING AN ICON – SHAMING THE PERPETRATORS – COUNTERING RAPE CULTURE: AFFECTIVE MEDIA PRACTICES IN NETWORKED FEMINISM ON TIKTOK

Annabella Backes (Freie Universität Berlin) and Margreth Lünenborg (Freie Universität Berlin).

The rise of digital platforms has transformed feminist activism, shaping how sexualized violence is discussed, witnessed, and resisted (Mendes et al., 2019). This paper examines the affective media practices (Lünenborg et al., 2021) content creators employ on TikTok in response to the Mazan rape cases in France, centering on survivor Gisèle Pelicot’s declaration, “shame must change sides,” which directly addresses the emotional dimension of rape culture and challenges its entrenched dynamics.

Drawing on a dataset of 280 TikTok posts collected via the TikTok Research API, our study investigates how feminist media practices emerge in response to sexualized violence, analyzing their affective dimensions (Ahmed, 2014). Drawing from feminist media studies and applying an affect-theoretical lens, we qualitatively analyze multimodal content to trace the performative emergence of bodies, practices, and discourse. Our analysis identifies five key affective media practices in networked feminism shaping the negotiation of the case on TikTok: (1) Feminist education positions the case within its broader socio-cultural and political frameworks, performing an affective spectrum from measured critique to cynical outrage; (2) Affective witnessing manifests as users publicly share their emotional responses—such as disbelief, fear, and sadness—thereby reinforcing collective affectedness; (3) Iconization positions Pelicot as a feminist heroine, aiming at shifting the shame away from her body and the discourse from victimhood to survivorship and leadership; (4) Shaming emerges as a strategic intervention to contest perpetrators’ social impunity, aligning with Pelicot’s call to shift the burden of shame onto perpetrator’s bodies; (5) Feminist intertextual cross-referencing connects the Mazan rape cases to wider feminist struggles, fostering transnational solidarities and interwoven activist narratives.

Our analysis reveals how content creators leverage platform affordances and affective media practices to tell the case their way and critique representations by media, lawyers, and the wider public. It also shows how TikTok serves as both a site of affective contestation and a vehicle for feminist mobilization (Anselmi et al., 2024; Slater, 2022), shaping affective responses to sexualized violence in an algorithmically structured, ephemeral, and diffuse digital environment (Özkula et al., 2024).

QUEERING MOTHERHOOD ON INSTAGRAM: SELF-REPRESENTATIONS OF ITALIAN LGBTQ+ MOTHERS BETWEEN UTOPIA AND TRADITION

Arianna Bussoletti (Sapienza University of Rome).

If media representations play a key role in expanding the definition of womanhood and motherhood, ambivalence in updating conservative narratives contributes to fostering exclusion and stereotypical representations, especially of LGBTQ+ people (Franchi & Selmi 2018). This is Italy’s case, where determinist understandings of gender, sexuality, and family find consensus in the public opinion and politics (Corbisiero & Monaco 2020). With the Italian mediascape being primarily man-owned and reluctant to provide representations of queer women and motherhood, digital platforms become an important environment from which LGBTQ+ mothers try to fill the gap left behind by traditional media. Through digital ethnography of five accounts of LGBTQ+ mother-influencers on Instagram, the

contribution investigates self-representations of both motherhood and queer femininity. Such method values queer media practices and individuals' agency in defining themselves. Preliminary results highlight that LGBTQ+ mother-influencers alternate between stereotypical and alternative representations. Most posts choose to focus on 'happy' children and 'traditional' family life to counter the narrative that sees LGBTQ+ mothers as selfish and unnatural. Political takes and alternative portrayals of motherhood, instead, often receive critiques, suggesting that the role of mother is still deeply anchored in tradition. LGBTQ+ mothers both weaponize and conform to it to prevent and address harassment and oppression, highlighting the challenges queer Italian families face. Despite this, all accounts show a tendency toward education and authenticity. Excluded from media decision-making processes, queer mothers turn to Instagram for self-representations, to educate publics, and to circumvent disinformation regarding their own lives. Albeit not free from harassment, digital platforms are environments where Italian LGBTQ+ mother-influencers can reshape mainstream media narratives. Given a relative lack of symbolic LGBTQ+ figures and events in Italy, LGBTQ+ mother-influencers can allow scholars a glimpse into these subjectivities' cultural and social presence, political involvement, and how they contend with networked antagonism, social expectations, and integration, negotiating identity-based stigma and building queer utopias through alternative models of gender, sexuality, and family.

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REPRESENTING IDEAL FEMININITY: HOW RELIGIOUS WOMEN NEGOTIATE MULTIPLE MARGINALISATIONS ON INSTAGRAM

Rachel Abreu (University of Stirling).

Social media are integral to representations of gender, race, and religion. Visual platforms like Instagram, however, are persistently dominated by normative portrayals of beauty and femininity. These portrayals subsequently contribute to the alienation and othering of those who do not conform to Eurocentric ideals. Using narratives from religious, ethnic minority women, this paper considers the challenges of expressing intersectional identities and raises the question of what positive, true-to-life representation looks like for women who face multiple marginalisations online.

Social media are often touted as contributing to cross-cultural engagement and greater acceptance of difference. Yet, representations of religious, ethnic minority women on Instagram continue to uphold Western perspectives that homogenise them into one ugly, oppressed group. Drawing on a larger research project on Instagram, beauty, and religious identity, this paper takes an interdisciplinary approach to understanding women's expectations for representation on social media. This paper uses in-depth focus groups and individual interviews with Muslim, Jewish, and Christian women located globally, with the aim of shifting focus to religious women's own criteria for ideal beauty, femininity, and representation. In doing so, this study emphasises the views of a group persistently stereotyped by colonial framings of identity.

The findings demonstrate the centrality of nuanced, lived experience to religious women's feelings of agency and belonging on Instagram. Specifically, opportunities for fostering communities of hybrid cultural identity and alternative, religious feminisms allow minority ethnic women to address persistent algorithmic bias and limited representation of multifaceted identities. Despite increasingly disheartened attitudes about diversity and representation on an individual level, participants' discussions also highlight their endeavours to take advantage of Instagram's tools and move beauty and femininity away from physical markers of identity. Ultimately, the research emphasises a distinction between

more and better representation and how this can be achieved for future generations of religious women.

RESISTING ERASURE, RECLAIMING SPACE: ENSURING MIGRANT AND RACIALISED WOMEN'S VOICES IN DIGITAL MEDIA

Juliana da Penha (Migrant Women Press)

As we approach the 30th anniversary of the Beijing Platform for Action, the digital era presents both new opportunities and significant challenges for marginalised women's communication rights. While independent media platforms play a crucial role in amplifying underrepresented voices, their long-term sustainability remains precarious. In the UK and beyond, media ownership concentration, limited pluralism, and scarce funding have created an environment where media outlets serving marginalised women struggle to survive—many are suffocating under financial constraints, while others have disappeared entirely. This paper presents a case study of Migrant Women Press, a migrant women-led independent media organisation, examining the business models and strategies necessary to sustain such platforms while maintaining journalistic independence. Drawing on consultancy research, audience engagement surveys, and case studies of nonprofit media outlets, the study evaluates Migrant Women Press through the media viability framework (Moore et al., 2024) and the three pillars of independent news sustainability (Dejarnette, 2021): financial health, organisational resilience, and journalism impact. Findings from a recent project delivered focused on gender-based violence suggest that partnerships with mission-aligned organisations can provide a sustainable revenue stream, reducing reliance on precarious, short-term funding cycles. The study further argues for hybrid business strategies, incorporating philanthropic grants, ethical advertising, and innovative multimedia formats (e.g., podcasts, documentaries) to increase audience engagement. It also advocates for recognising journalism as a public good that must be supported with adequate structural and financial conditions. By addressing the intersections of gender, migration, race, and media sustainability, this paper contributes to broader discussions on women's digital rights and the right to self-representation in media. It calls for a rethinking of traditional media funding models and urges policymakers, funders, and media stakeholders to support inclusive, independent journalism, ensuring that migrant and racialised women not only participate in the digital media landscape but actively shape its future.

SELLING GENDER: THE ROLE OF ADVERTISING IN (RE)PRODUCING STEREOTYPICAL GENDER NARRATIVES

Ajohche Nkemngu Awungjia (The University of the Western Cape).

The relationship between media and society has been the subject of extensive research due to the media's ability to influence social attitudes, behaviours, and opportunities across cultures and contexts. Within the context of gender, the media can both reinforce and/or challenge existing gender ideologies and hierarchies. Despite the significant strides that have been made towards improving the quality of women's lives in education, civil rights, employment and other societal sectors, the media - particularly advertising - remain highly dependent on stereotypical representations in crafting visual messages. Although there has been an increase in calls for and efforts towards more authentic gender representation in media, stereotypical representations remain deeply embedded in our visual and narrative landscape.

In this paper, we ask: How do online advertising practices perpetuate dominant gender stereotypes, and what transformative equality and feminist interventions are needed to promote more authentic representations? This study draws on a systematic literature review and a content analysis of 700 online advertisements from five countries—The Netherlands, Spain, South Africa, Belgium, and Poland—to examine how advertising constructs gendered meanings. We conducted a chi-square test and Cramér's V test, which revealed a significant relationship between gender and key narrative elements, such as the product being advertised, the role played by the model, the basis of their credibility, and their spatial positioning within the advertisement. This finding suggests that the narratives created around models or central figures in advertisements are not random but are instead structured in ways that (re)produce dominant gender norms. However, cross-country comparisons showed that the extent and intensity of these differences in representation vary significantly by country, pointing to additional cultural, regulatory, or market-driven factors that shape advertising practices. In doing so, we consider what interventions in the form of media regulation, activism, and industry shifts can challenge dominant narratives and create space for more inclusive, equitable representations.

SEXIST ONLINE HATE SPEECH ON VIDEO PLATFORMS: RESULTS OF FIVE CONTENT ANALYSES

M. Rohangis Mohseni (TU Ilmenau) and Nicola Döring (TU Ilmenau).

Rationale: Sexist discrimination against women is an ongoing problem. A modern type of sexist discrimination is Online Hate Speech (OHS). Women may be generally more often the target of OHS than men; and women may be specifically more often the target of sexist OHS than men (Jane, 2016; Wotanis & McMillan, 2014). This disparity can disadvantage women who try to participate actively online (Molyneaux et al. 2008). However, there are not many studies on OHS against women. Research is particularly needed on video platforms because they are among the widest-reaching online platforms.

Objective: This study investigated if women on video platforms are more often the target of OHS than men (RQ1), and if women are more often the target of specifically sexist OHS than men (RQ2). Sexist OHS included hate speech that denigrated the target's gender as well as comments that sexually objectified or threatened the target.

Methods: The study by Wotanis and McMillan (2014) on sexist OHS on YouTube was chosen for five replications (1: North-American YouTubers from original study; 2: comparable North-American YouTubers; 3: People depicted in fail videos; 4: German YouTubers; 5: German YouNowers). Five manual quantitative content analyses with a total of $N = 24.244$ publicly available video comments were conducted. **Results:** In three of five studies, women on video platforms were generally significantly more often the target of OHS than men (RQ1), and women were specifically significantly more often the target of sexist hate speech than men (RQ2).

Discussion: Results indicate that there is a certain pattern of sexist OHS on video platforms, but also that other factors play a role.

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SILENCING SCIENCE: THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL VIOLENCE AGAINST FEMALE RESEARCHERS

Nina Vischer (Regensburg University of Applied Science (OTH Regensburg)), Kyra Schneider (Regensburg University of Applied Science (OTH Regensburg)).

Gender-based digital violence is on the rise, as is hostility towards science. Digital violence threatens not only gender equality in academia but also equal participation of women in the (digital) public sphere. This is where the research project “Digital Hate - Digital violence against female professors in contentious fields of knowledge” comes in. As female professors become more visible with their innovative research, they can also be exposed to digital violence such as hate speech, doxing or sexual harassment. This project investigates the extent, forms, content and effects of gender-based digital violence against academics, specifically female professors in Germany working in the fields of gender, migration or climate research. Furthermore, the institutional strategies and support structures against digital hate in academia will be examined. The results of the first stage of the project, a quantitative online questionnaire characterizing female researchers’ exposure and attitudes to digital violence as well as the degree of institutional support, will be presented at the conference. In addition, the next phases of this mixed methods project, namely characterization of institutional responses as well as qualitative interviews with survivors of anti-science digital hate, will be outlined, and an open dialog with conference participants on countermeasures against digital gender-based violence is anticipated. Ultimately, the project aims to contribute to the development of effective support measures and counterstrategies to reduce the detrimental effects of gender-based, anti-science digital hate.

STRATEGIES OF NEGOTIATION, CONFRONTATION, AND OVERCOMING VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN IN POLITICAL PRACTICE ON SOCIAL MEDIA IN COSTA RICA

Yanet Martinez Toledo (Centro de Investigación en Comunicación, Universidad de Costa Rica).

This work analyzes the strategies implemented by women politicians in Costa Rica to confront digital political violence, highlighting its intersectional dimension. The research acknowledges that this violence not only infringes upon fundamental rights but also reproduces structural dynamics of exclusion, aiming to delegitimize women and restrict their participation in the public sphere. It combines factors such as gender, age, ideological affiliation, ethnic origin, and social class, further deepening existing inequalities (Baker & Juarasz, 2019).

The study employed a qualitative approach with an intersectional perspective to understand how multiple identities influence experiences of violence. Twenty-two in-depth interviews were conducted with women politicians who held office between 2014 and 2022, including congresswomen and ministers. Additionally, the political use of their social media profiles was analyzed to document the aggressions they faced and the responses they developed (Losch & Wernimont, 2018).

The findings reveal multiple forms of digital violence, including sexualized comments, direct threats, and mansplaining. These aggressions target not only their political work but also their personal lives, with references to their bodies, families, and relationships (Shokooh-Valle, 2020).

Key strategies identified include depersonalizing social media profiles, using digital platforms to amplify gender-related issues, and relying on professional support teams. This analysis underscores that violence does not affect all women equally and highlights the need for intersectional public policies to ensure safe participation.

SUSTAINABILITY OF LIFE AT THE HEART OF TRANSFORMATIVE FEMINIST COMMUNICATION: NEW HORIZONS FOR JOURNALISTS

María Sánchez-Ramos (University of Seville), Laura Martínez-Jiménez (Miguel de Cervantes European University) and Belén Zurbano-Brenguer (University of Seville).

The big media conglomerates set themselves up as ‘agencies of the superstructures’ (Gramsci in Hall, 1981: 238) that naturalise the patriarchal neoliberal capitalist system and (re)present it as the only possible model of social organisation. In the face of this predatory system that exploits living beings and natural resources in a seemingly unlimited growth, feminist thinkers have articulated heterodox and critical proposals that put (good) life at the centre. This transition towards other modes of production, consumption and social organisation prioritises the harmonious and integral relationship between human beings and nature to enable the conditions for developing capacities and life projects in a fair way. This work is based on the hypothesis that social communication, and specifically journalism, can and must contribute to placing the care and interdependence of lives at the centre, within the framework of a transformative socio-economic project that goes beyond neoliberalism. The research, which is part of the project ‘Feminist journalism. The importance of communication with a gender perspective’ (University of Malaga), presents a methodology based on a literature review and in-depth interviews with nine feminist journalism professionals. The results provide a cartography of the ecofeminist qualities of journalism and draw an intersectional roadmap that includes this other way of doing journalism, with its requirements/demands/obstacles and horizons from the perspective of “transformative feminist communication” (Laura Martínez-Jiménez et al., 2023a). Among the conclusions, it is worth highlighting that the sustainability of life as a professional, labour-organisational and personal-political foundation of journalism is only possible in alliance with grassroots and popular, anti-capitalist and intersectional feminisms.

TACKLING CYBER VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN AND GIRLS: EIGE’S WORK ON MEASURING FORMS OF ONLINE GENDERED VIOLENCE

Monica Barbovschi (European Institute for Gender Equality).

Cyberviolence against women and girls (CVAWG) is pervasive and growing. Especially considering VLOPs and VLSEs (Very Large Online Platforms / Search Engines) recently rolling back on human and women’s rights, EU policy makers need to understand this phenomenon and combat it. Additional challenges in these efforts are brought by the fragmentation of legal and statistical definitions across EU Member States jurisdictions, as well as the platforms’ own trust and safety policies and practices (often developed with gender-neutral lens), which make it difficult to identify and combat various CVAWG as forms of gender-based violence.

The European Union’s Knowledge Centre on Gender Equality, (EIGE, located in Vilnius), supports policy makers in the EU (and beyond) in efforts to achieve gender equality and eradicate all forms of violence against women and girls. EIGE’s recent research includes a comprehensive mapping of forms of CVAWG (2021) involving all 27 Member States (MS) by means of a mixed methodology (review of national literature and policies, interviews with stakeholders, analysis of existing definitions and terminology), provision of gender-based definitions for a series of forms of violence (2022), and development of indicators on four forms of CVAWG (2023), equivalent to those criminalised by the EU Directive 1385/2024 on Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (Cyber-stalking, Cyber-harassment, Online gender-based hate speech, non-consensual dissemination of intimate and manipulated material). This measurement framework could be implemented both through survey methodologies and populated through administrative data sources, thus enabling consistent and

comparable data collection across the 27 member states. Finally, EIGE conducted a policy analysis on the role of online platforms, focusing on the rules and definitions, and the reporting mechanisms in place together with the recording of cases (2023-2024). The findings revealed several key challenges in online platforms' approach to CVAWG. This presentation will outline the findings of these engagements.

TALKS WITH PIONEER WOMEN IN COMMUNICATION STUDIES IN PORTUGAL

Filipa Subtil (LIACOM/ESCS-IPL), Susana Torrado-Morales (Facultad de Comunicación y Documentación, Universidad de Murcia), Maribel Olmos (Facultad de Comunicación y Documentación, Universidad de Murcia) and Marisa Torres da Silva (ICNOVA/NOVA FCSH).

Systematic research into women researchers in Communication studies is recent. In the Anglo-Saxon context, the task of accounting for the feminine from epistemological perspectives, e.g. analysing the role of women academics in shaping the scientific field of Communication, has been underway for just over a decade (Simonson & Archer, 2011; Vera-Balanza, 2012; Dorsten, 2012 and 2016; Rowland & Simonson, 2013; García-Jiménez & Simonson, 2021; García-Jiménez, 2019 and 2021; García-Jiménez & Simonson, 2021; Herrero, 2024). In the Ibero-American context, research on this topic began more recently and is now beginning to show results (Gobbi, 2023a; 2023b; García-Jiménez et al., 2022; García-Jiménez & Herrero, 2025; Heram & Gándara, 2021; Lazcano-Peña y Reyes-Lillo, 2020). In the Portuguese context, the inclusion of women in university teaching and research in Communication and media began in 1979 at Nova University of Lisbon, where the first bachelor degree in Social Communication was created with a teaching staff largely formed by men (Mendes, 2012; Ribeiro, 2016; Serra, 2017). In the early years, the team of researchers and lecturers included four women, who had no management or leadership positions in the teams. A curious fact is that the first doctoral thesis in Social Communication at Nova University of Lisbon was presented by a woman, Chaké Matoussian. The increase in the presence of women in teaching, research and institutional management only began to change towards the end of the 1980s and in the following decade, accompanying the formation of other departments and bachelor's, master's and doctoral programmes in various public higher education institutions. To date, there has been no research into the roles and scientific contributions of these pioneers in the institutions they passed through. This is why within the FEMICOMI project (femicom.es) we are analysing the main figures and experiences of pioneering women researchers in Communication in Latin America, Spain and Portugal. The aim of this contribution is to show the results of in-depth interviews with 6 pioneers in Communication research in Portugal: Maria Belo, Isabel Ferin Cunha, Maria Augusta Babo, Chaké Matoussian, Isabel Nobre Vargues and Maria João Silveirinha. We want to highlight the work of these researchers who began their careers in the 1980s in the Portuguese field of Communications in order to give them and their contributions the visibility they have been denied for decades. The interview questions revolve around their careers, the roles of women researchers, the opportunities and structural obstacles they faced, leadership, motherhood, gender stereotypes and the situation of women in Portuguese academia.

TECH FOR WOMEN: AN INTERDISCIPLINARY ACTIVIST AND INCLUSION STUDY WITH BRAZILIAN AND PORTUGUESE COMMUNITIES

Renata Frade (University of Aveiro).

This research examines how women's tech communities in Brazil and Portugal utilize storytelling as a tool for collective activism, empowerment, and professional inclusion. The study analyzes the information-communication processes that emerge within these communities and their impact on women's participation in technology fields. The methodology combines digital ethnography with observer participatory and participatory design research, involving interviews with community leaders and members, content analysis of digital platforms and focus groups. Initial findings reveal how these communities create alternative spaces for knowledge sharing and professional development while challenging traditional patriarchal structures in technology. The research highlights the importance of intersectional perspectives in understanding how factors such as geographical location, social class, and cultural background influence women's experiences in tech. This work contributes to discussions about feminist media practices in the Global South, offering insights into how digital platforms can be leveraged for building solidarity networks and promoting gender equality in traditionally male-dominated fields. The findings have implications for policy development regarding women's inclusion in STEM fields and the role of community-led initiatives in addressing gender disparities in technology sectors.

THE ROLLBACK OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN FAR-RIGHT PROPAGANDA

Jazmin Duarte Sckell (Freie Universität Berlin).

The authoritarian far-right has shaped the Latin American continent, first with the rise of anti-gender “pro-family” campaigns in 2016, and then with the successful election of far-right presidents such as Jair Bolsonaro in Brazil in 2018 and Javier Milei in 2023. There has been a clear collaboration between the different reactionary sectors, where gender and anti-feminism have functioned as symbolic glue and common ground around which to devise their campaigns of fear. The mixture of anti-feminist and misogynist discourses, in different types of messages issued by the far-right, represents the consolidation of a fertile ground for the justification of the rollback of women's and diversity rights. This article analyses some notable examples of far-right propaganda, which clearly illustrate the intention, sometimes not so explicit, to place women in subordinate positions and to roll back rights. It will also include examples of specific cases of the far-right in government, and the negative effects they have had in the area of rights for women and diversities. This mapping seeks to highlight the challenges we face in this new context, in search of devising our strategies of resistance.

THE SEXIST AND AGEIST VISUAL IMAGERY OF GENERATIVE AI SYSTEMS: HOW TEXT-TO-IMAGE TECHNOLOGIES MAKE FEMALE AGING INVISIBLE

Beatrice Melis (Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa & Gran Sasso Science Institute), Gianluca De Ninno (Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa & Gran Sasso Science Institute) and Francesca Belotti (Department of Human Studies, University of L'Aquila).

This paper addresses the sexism and ageism embedded in generative artificial intelligence systems (genAIs) focusing on their visual outputs. While research on gender-based biases in genAIs is growing (Browne et al., 2023; Sandoval-Martin & Martínez-Sanzo, 2024; Toupin, 2024 among others), analyses of the age-based ones are still incipient (Putland et al., 2023; Byrne et al., 2024; Loos et al., 2024) and even fewer explore their intersection (Sadeghiani, 2024; Zhou et al., 2024). This study seeks to bridge this gap by demonstrating how genAIs' outputs systematically overrepresent young men while rendering (older) women invisible. The theoretical framework draws upon incipient studies on the socio-cultural component of AI systems (Airoldi, 2022; Natale & Depounti, 2024; Gillespie, 2024) and their vocation to interact as actual communicators (Esposito, 2022; Natale & Guzman, 2022; Bolin,

2024). We focus on genAIs (namely, ChatGPT-4o) because they generate apparently authentic but not necessarily accurate content (Hacker et al., 2024; Chan et al., 2024), which makes them at risk of (re)producing misleading narratives. Moreover, we focus on their visual outputs since images are impactful carriers of cultural repertoires (Wright, 2008). We designed a series of prompts to elicit images depicting different daily activities, and differentiated the chats in three threads: one dedicated to individual activities, another one to activity domains, and the last one to a semi-structured interview with the chatbot explaining the generated images. We carried out critical visual analysis (Schroeder 2006) of the images and critical discourse analysis (Machin & Mayr 2012) of the interview. Preliminary results show that sexism and ageism jointly operate in all aspects of text-to-image synthesis, reinforcing a visual imaginary that privileges young masculinity while marginalizing female aging. This points to the gender- and age-based biases that intervene in genAIs' design, development and usage, while hinting at a pink washing operation undertaken by tech companies.

TRANS WOMEN'S COMMUNICATIVE RIGHTS IN ANTI-GENDER TIMES: RESISTANCE AND RESILIENCE IN DIGITAL SPACES

Liv Izgi (Södertörn University).

Through digital ethnographic observation of TERF discourse on Turkish-language Twitter/X, this study examines how exclusionary feminist narratives shape and constrain the communicative rights of trans women. By analyzing the rhetorical and affective mechanisms underpinning these narratives, the research highlights the ways in which online hostility restricts trans women's ability to participate in public discourse, assert their identities, and engage in knowledge production.

Simultaneously, an autoethnographic "affective diary" records the emotional toll of encountering and responding to digital transphobia, providing an embodied account of the communicative struggles faced by trans individuals. The findings indicate that TERF discourse not only generates ontological insecurity and emotional exhaustion for trans women but also paradoxically strengthens their self-awareness and collective resilience. This tension underscores the dual role of digital platforms as both spaces of marginalization and sites for resistance, where trans women continuously reclaim their right to voice their lived experiences.

Moreover, the study demonstrates that digital transphobia operates beyond interpersonal hostility, reinforcing systemic authoritarian policies that further restrict trans women's communicative agency. By naturalizing dehumanization, these narratives serve to legitimize broader social and political exclusions, limiting trans women's access to both discursive and material resources.

By integrating affective feminist phenomenology with digital discourse analysis, this study contributes to feminist and trans studies by centering the communicative rights of trans women within digital gender debates. It also expands autoethnography as a method for capturing the lived experiences of marginalized communities in online spaces. Ultimately, this research highlights the urgent need to protect trans women's digital communicative rights, recognizing that identity is not only discursively shaped but also affectively and politically negotiated within digital environments.

WHEN A MAN HATES A WOMAN: NARRATIVE AND LINGUISTIC STRATEGIES OF BRAZIL'S MANOSPHERE ON YOUTUBE

Debora Salles (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro), Luciane Leopoldo Belin (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro), Adriano Belisario (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro) and Marie Santini (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro).

Research has shown that digital platforms have been leveraged to target women online and cultivate hostile communities. However, little is known about how communities such as the “manosphere” and its discursive strategies are used by online content creators to perpetuate long-standing patriarchal gender ideologies in non-anglophone contexts. In Brazil, the online manosphere has been gaining ground, especially over social media and YouTube. This research aims to analyze the narratives and discursive strategies adopted by Brazilian content creators on YouTube’s manosphere as a means to connect and build digital communities based on masculinist ideals and misogyny. By combining computational and qualitative analyses, we analyzed 76,289 videos, published by 7,812 channels, to observe how content creators use YouTube channels to disseminate masculinist narratives. Firstly, we employed computational topic modelling of the collected video titles, then we qualitatively evaluated the results and synthesized them into eight main themes: 1) Contempt for Women and Male Insurgency; 2) Seduction and Relationships; 3) Defense of Traditional Gender Roles; 4) Antifeminism; 5) Male Development; 6) Legal Issues; and 7) Political Content. Secondly, we employed critical discourse analysis (CDA) to analyze content representative of each theme, which enabled us to investigate the content beyond the sentence level, scrutinizing how content creators employ a variety of textual and visual strategies to reinforce masculinist narratives. These include specific vocabulary, sensationalist and degrading imagery, and humor as tools to discursively ridicule women and mock feminism. Our results highlight the growth of the manosphere community on Brazilian YouTube and emphasize the urgent need for more effective moderation tools, informed by linguistic and visual analysis, to identify and mitigate online hate speech against women. By integrating computational tools with qualitative methods, this study offers a comprehensive analysis of the manosphere’s discursive strategies and their broader socio-political implications.

WHOSE VOICES MATTER?: MARGINALIZED FEMINISMS IN THE LUSOPHONE FEMINIST DIGITAL SPHERE

Camila Lamartine (ICNOVA, NOVA FCSH).

Thirty years after the Beijing Platform for Action, feminist movements continue to navigate a media landscape that remains exclusionary and structurally unequal. While digital platforms have amplified feminist voices, they have also reinforced hegemonic narratives that marginalize non-white, decolonial, and subaltern feminist perspectives. This paper introduces the concept of Marginalized Feminisms, which interrogates the racialized, classed, and colonial structures embedded in mainstream feminist discourse, particularly in the digital sphere. By analyzing cyberfeminist activism in Portugal and Brazil, this study explores how Black, Indigenous, and immigrant feminist representatives challenge the white-centric digital feminist landscape and create counter-hegemonic spaces of resistance. Drawing on intersectional feminist theory (Akotirente, 2019; Collins & Bilge, 2020), postcolonial critique (Spivak, 1988; Kilomba, 2019), and digital media studies (Chamberlain, 2017; Banet-Weiser, 2018), this research examines the paradox of visibility: while marginalized feminists gain recognition in online spaces, their voices are often co-opted, tokenized, or subjected to heightened digital misogyny and racialized violence. This study critically engages with the limitations of Beijing’s Section J by questioning whose voices are truly included in feminist media discourses and policy frameworks.

Ultimately, the paper argues that cyberfeminist activism must move beyond representation towards structural transformations in media governance, platform policies, and transnational feminist solidarities, especially considering the fourth wave. By centering Marginalized Feminisms within discussions of intersectional discrimination and white feminism supremacy, this research contributes to the broader dialogue on feminist media justice and decolonial futures in cyberfeminism and digital communication.

WOMEN'S VOICES IN MILITARIZED MEDIA DISCOURSES: STRATEGIES FOR PEACE-BUILDING COMMUNICATION

Olena Zinenko (V.N.Karazin KhNU, School of Sociology, Ukraine, IFHV, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany) and Olga Syniugina (Kharkiv Regional Foundation "Public Alternative", Ukraine; Outlier Platform, USA).

The mediatization of war takes various forms and employs diverse strategies. Social media users predominantly reinforce war narratives, while peaceful campaigns are frequently criticized or disregarded as irrelevant. Peace understanding in Ukraine is negatively perceived due to Russian disinformation, where counter-narratives often reinforce the inverted meaning. Women's voices remain insufficiently represented, often silenced or overshadowed by opposition campaigns. Double mediatization of people's needs allows influencers and officials to exploit discussions on vulnerable groups for self-promotion and illiberal control. Social media serve as crucial tools for transforming conflict into platforms for communication. The traditional understanding of media as a space reinforcing stereotype is evolving. Media platforms facilitate feminist activism and counter-narratives against societal norms and advocate for better female representation in film and television, social media movements globally challenge sexual harassment and increasingly function as an instrument for structural change and policy advocacy. The research investigates communication strategies for women's needs in militarized discourse to build a model of peace-building communication to be applied in the Ukrainian context to provide a framework of application for other war contexts. Based on discussions of women's peace tables and media monitoring in 2020-2024 the study decodes collective memory about the concepts of 'peace' and 'peacebuilding' and explores the communication strategies in social media (over a million social media messages) to counter prevailing war narratives and foster recovery and reconciliation. The study highlights the role of media access by women experts and emphasizes the role of activist networks in consolidating efforts for political advocacy, using cases from Ukraine and global peace-building initiatives (Colombia, Nepal, Palestina, Bosnia and Herzegovina).

WORKING WOMEN REPRESENTATIONS IN CONTEMPORARY SPANISH CINEMA (1975-2025): MOVING TOWARDS ECONOMIC EMANCIPATION AND THE CRITIQUE OF THE "CRISIS OF CARE"

Núria Araüna Baró (Universitat Rovira i Virgili).

The historical invisibility of women's formal and informal labor has obscured their economic contributions and their role as agents of social change (Arbaiza, 2014). In Spanish cinema, the Transition period marked a turning point, as working women began to gain visibility, leading to the portrayal of more emancipated and independent female subjectivities, no longer defined mainly by their relationships with male characters or family. Since then, three key models of working women have emerged: 1) The middle-upper-class professional woman, often depicted in prestigious occupations. This figure appears in what Vernon (2011) termed the "feminist trilogy" of the Transition, directed by

women: *Vámonos, Bárbara* (Cecilia Bartolomé, 1978), *Gary Cooper, que estás en los cielos* (Josefina Molina, 1980), and *Función de Noche* (Josefina Molina, 1981) and proliferates vastly since the 2000s. 2) The working-class woman, whose historical significance in the 19th century was later erased to "sanitize" the image of the working class (Arbaiza, 2014). This figure reemerged in militant cinema, such as the works of the *Colectivo Cine de Clase* and films like *Numax presenta...* (Joaquim Jordá, 1979) and has gained weight again after the 2008 recession. 3) The small business owner, exemplified by Carmen Maura's hairdresser in *¿Qué hace una chica como tú en un sitio como este?* (Fernando Colomo, 1978), the iconic tobacco seller in *La Estanquera de Vallecas* (Eloy de la Iglesia, 1987) or many of Almodóvar's lead characters. Examining the evolution of these three models in subsequent decades allows us to observe the diversification of women's representation in the workplace and across social classes, as well as the tensions between the emancipation that wage labor can offer and the persistence of patriarchal norms. At the same time, the rise of neoliberal rationality and the growing "crisis of care" (Frazer, 2014) have deeply affected worker women's scripts and images in recent films.

PANEL

FEMINIST MOVEMENTS, COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA IN PORTUGAL: REFLECTIONS FROM FEMGLOCAL PROJECT

Overview

Gender's political relevance is growing, both its institutionalization at national and supra-national entities, and its mobilization as a phantasm (Butler, 2024) for far-right movements. Besides the academic exploration around issues of representation, which often assumes a simplistic approach between media exposure and media effects, research has also focused on the agencements of gender as performed through media - while still connected to material realities. It is to give an account of the multiple and situated efforts and developments of feminist action - as well as its ambivalent connection with mediatization, and with digital spaces in specific - that this panel brings together an integrated view of which feminisms have been at play in and through Portugal, and how.

BETWEEN THE PAST AND PRESENT OF PORTUGUESE FEMINIST ACTIVISM

Célia Taborda, CICANT - Lusófona University

Feminist activism in Portugal has followed a trajectory marked by advances and setbacks from the 19th century to the present day. The First Republic (1910–1934) was a milestone in the affirmation of feminism in the country, allowing the emergence of feminist associations strongly focused on voting rights and education. However, the vibrancy of these early movements faded with the dictatorship that followed the fall of the First Republic. The *Estado Novo* regime succeeded in erasing the historical memory of these feminisms by dissolving associations such as the National Council of Portuguese Women, leading feminist activism to merge with anti-fascist struggles (Tavares, 2011).

With the establishment of democracy in 1974, activism re-emerged. In 1979, the CNAC (National Campaign for Abortion and Contraception) was created, bringing together various feminist associations and individual women advocating for the decriminalization of abortion and against gender-based violence. In the following years, new associations and movements emerged, bringing feminist demands into the

public sphere, particularly those related to bodily autonomy, sexuality, labor equality, and gender-based violence.

Contemporary feminisms in Portugal seek to align themselves with international feminist movements in terms of both mobilization and action. They use digital platforms and take to the streets, incorporating global feminist struggles into their agendas while maintaining the specific dynamics of local activism. Recent examples of this include engagement with the #MeToo movement and the International Feminist Strike.

Thirty years after the Beijing Conference, and despite the achievements of feminism since then, feminist movements still face numerous challenges, especially in countries like Portugal, where historical factors have constrained feminist activism. This issue was explored in the FEMglocal project and will be analyzed in this presentation.

THE ACADEMIC CONSTRUCTION OF “WOMAN” IN PORTUGUESE COMMSCI - NOTES ON BOUNDARIES, NAMINGS AND HEGEMONIES

Daniel Cardoso, CICANT - Lusófona University , FCSH - NOVA University of Lisbon

Departing from an in-development scoping literature review regarding the use of “cisgender” in a subset of Portuguese academia focused on Media and Communication Studies, I look at the presence and absence of how “woman”/“women” are (un-)specified, to argue that the academic construction of “the Woman” in this field is still predicated on essentialist, cisnormative understandings of gender as existing within two (sometimes overlapping) binaries: masculine/feminine and hegemonic/disadvantaged. The reiteration of this dual binary contributes to a semiotic un-marking of sameness (qua epistemicide (Fricker, 2007; Haraway, 1988)) and, thus, a reinforced Othering of subordinated femininities in service of an ontological stabilization of “the Woman”, potentially in service of an affirmation and institutionalization of Feminist and Gender Studies in Portugal. As a suggested way out of this erasure, I recall the work done by queerfeminist activists (qua epistemic community (Antoniades, 2003; Haas, 2021)), and reflect on how the (digital) mapping performed by the FEMGlocal project should be properly understood as existing at the intersection of bibliographic reference and data source.

OPINION, REPRESENTATION, AND REACTION: FEMINIST ACTIVISM IN THE OPINION COLUMNS

Sónia Lamy, CICANT - Lusófona University

Opinion plays an essential role in the media construction of public space, surpassing the typically more closed discourse coming from informative institutions, to allow plural debate and the exercise of freedom of expression, both protecting and provoking the public space (Kovach and Rosenstiel, 2003, p. 197). The framing of feminist movements and collectives arises from the news published in newspapers and the opinions conveyed in this space.

Journalism amplifies voices and can contribute to a more inclusive and equitable society, by bringing certain topics to be debated; however, not all published news is informative.

The opinion space in the media intersects with the history of international journalism, constituting itself as media discourse and contributing to the representation of certain social spaces. Most newspapers clearly define the opinion space, and not only clarify their objectives but also often set the purposes, rules, and boundaries within which it operates. Many newspapers, in their style guides (Público, 2005; El Mundo, n/d), clarify news genres as non-informative spaces, making sure to draw boundaries and ensure that there is no intrusion or contamination between the two. Assuming that the articles published encourage breaking culturally imposed silences and potentially influencing the way certain topics are understood and

publicly received (Cerqueira et al., 2023), we propose an analysis of a space, by nature, of argumentative freedom. This paper aims to offer a published opinion on feminist movements and collectives, based on a corpus of 370 news items published on the websites of the newspapers Expresso, Público, JN, Observador, Correio da Manhã, and the two newsmagazines Sábado and Visão, between 2011 and 2022. The research was conducted on the MediaCloud platform using the keywords feminist organisations/associations/movements;, but in this study, we will focus on 43 opinion articles, which we will characterize by the variables month and year of publication, the newspaper in which it was published, the genre of the opinion article, the theme that serves as a basis, the starting point for the article, and the author, based on the following research questions: Q1: Who gives voice to opinions focused on feminist activism? Q2: What topics mobilize the opinion conveyed in the articles? Q3: Are opinion spaces reactions to current events? We aim to propose a reflection on the type of feminist construction focused on the media discourse made within the freer spaces of opinion.

WHO WRITES ABOUT FEMINISMS IN PORTUGAL: AN ANALYSIS OF #METOO AND 8M

Carla Cerqueira, CICANT, Lusófona University

In this presentation I focus on the producers of journalistic discourse about the transnational feminist movements analysed as part of the FEMglocal project, namely #MeToo and the 8M Feminist Strike. These movements have made it possible to discuss various issues and put them on the public agenda, such as harassment and other forms of sexual violence, domestic labour, among others. However, there is also an ambivalence in themes and approaches. Serious discussion of these issues is mixed with anti-feminist discourses that seek to discredit the causes and their protagonists. It is in this meander of contradictions found in the analyses of the news coverage that it is also important to reflect on who is in the sphere of production. This interrelationship between production and content is central to the political economy of the media, which is crucial for feminist studies.

With this purpose I set out to analyse who writes in the opinion spaces (chronicles, opinion articles, commentaries, open letters, essays, opinion notes and editorials) in the Portuguese mainstream press: I focus on the authors published in the digital versions of the newspapers Público and Expresso. According to Tabada (2022), opinion spaces in the mainstream media reflect the dominant journalistic culture, but also include emerging and oppositional voices, particularly those of women (who are often relegated to the peripheries of communication).

It is therefore important to understand who places what emphasis, in regards to what has happened in the Portuguese iteration of transnational feminist movements with high visibility in the public space, such as #MeToo and the 8M Feminist Strike.

“THIS MANUAL IS FOR YOU!”: BUILDING A PRACTICAL TOOL AGAINST HARASSMENT IN THE AUDIOVISUAL SECTOR IN PORTUGAL

Ana Sofia Pereira, CICANT, Lusófona University and Camila Lamartine, ICNOVA, NOVA University of Lisbon

Workplace harassment is a structural issue across various professional sectors, including cinema and audiovisual, where informal employment relationships and rigid hierarchies create significant barriers to reporting and accountability. In Portugal, where the audiovisual sector is predominantly composed of small-scale productions, professionals, regardless of gender, face instability and precarious employment. However, women are disproportionately affected by discrimination and harassment. According to The Condition of Women in the Cinema and Audiovisual Sectors in Portugal (Burnay et al., 2023), 41.6% of women report experiencing gender discrimination, while 37.6% have been subjected to workplace

harassment. This study also highlights two critical dynamics that reinforce exclusion and impunity: the infantilization of women and the masculinist “boys’ club” culture.

FEMglocal, a research project exploring glocal feminist movements in Portugal, collaborates closely with feminist associations to promote gender equality. One of its case studies examined the impact of #MeToo in Portugal, a context where sector-specific tools to prevent and address harassment in the audiovisual industry remain largely absent. To help bridge this gap, FEMglocal researchers, in partnership with MUTIM – an association advocating for gender equality in film and audiovisual – developed the Manual Against Harassment in the Audiovisual Sector, the first tool of its kind in Portugal. This research seeks to explore how this manual can contribute to preventing and mitigating workplace harassment in Portugal’s audiovisual sector.

Built through a participatory process, the manual combines pedagogical and practical approaches, providing accessible guidelines for victims/survivors, witnesses, and employers. It addresses harassment identification, reporting mechanisms, and support systems, while also proposing a code of conduct and internal reporting channels. By integrating national legislation, international frameworks, and industry best practices, the manual addresses a critical gap in the Portuguese audiovisual sector. It stands as a replicable model, contributing to fostering a culture of respect and gender equality across creative industries.

PLENARY PANEL

EMPOWERING THE NEXT GENERATION: BUILDING FEMINIST SOLIDARITIES IN AND THROUGH MEDIA (EDUCATION)

Lucia Gloria Vázquez-Rodríguez; Alice Lima Baroni; Claudia Padovani

This panel underscores the critical importance of engaging younger generations in addressing gender equality in media, particularly in actualizing Section J of the Beijing Platform for Action on its 30th anniversary.

Through a teaching partnership developed within the EU-CERV funded project *Rewriting the Story* and expanded through subsequent international collaborations between 2022 and 2025, we provided students across different European Universities (Padova, Zagreb, Vienna, Gothenburg, Malta, Sydney) with the freedom to explore topics they identified as most pressing in the representation of women in media. By prioritizing their concerns, and acknowledging their creative competence and critical thinking skills, we argue that the voices of this generation can and should help shape future pedagogical and research interventions to tackle gender biases in media.

The implementation of inclusive feminist pedagogies (Bradbury-Rance, 2020; Morris, 2020; Crabtree & Sapp, Freire, 1970; 2003; hooks, 1994; Peauchaud, 2021) has been central to this initiative. And so has been the possibility to translate our own collaborative practices across Europe and beyond into reflections on critical pedagogies in gender and media higher education (see for example French, Padovani & Vega-Montiel, 2019; Ross & Padovani, 2021; Vázquez Rodríguez, García-Ramos, & Sánchez Gómez, 2020; Vazquez & Rozgony forthcoming). Participatory approaches and multimodal, creative outputs that transcend traditional academic formats have empowered students to engage more deeply. Knowing that their work would be publicly presented at the end of course, showcased on the AGEMI platform (www.agemi-eu.org) and used by media professionals, students approached gender equality themes with heightened commitment.

Our presentation will highlight key reflections and lessons from this experience, with an invitation to consider the need for future partnership to be established not only between academics and instructors but with groups of students themselves. To support this position, we shall feature in a creative and multimodal format, a selection of student final projects that address three central themes identified as relevant by our class groups: AI and Gender Justice (students developed a guidebook for teachers after testing AI as a self-education tool on gender and media); LGBTIQ+ representation in media, incorporating intersectional (Crenshaw, 1989) perspectives often absent in feminist work (students elaborated guidelines for LGBTIQ+ representation building on research and advocacy practices); and the media representation of women politicians, with contributions that challenge a Eurocentric lens (students produced visual materials and online resources then used to train journalists by the International Federation of Journalists).

Rooted in feminist pedagogies that seek to make students' work visible and valued, our approach ensures continuity with previous Feminist Media scholarship while providing mentorship. The intercultural and transnational dialogues fostered in our diverse classrooms—complemented by public events such as a two-day Marathon co-organized with the UniTWIN Network on Gender, Media, and ICT, where experts and professionals engaged with students' proposals and offered feedback—have generated deeply insightful and inspiring reflections, which students shared in their learning journals, an assessment method aligned with feminist pedagogies (Clifford, 2002).

Building on this experience, we emphasize the importance of cultivating transgenerational solidarities within and through media and communication, maintaining a strong commitment to Section J of the Beijing Platform for Action. We argue that forging meaningful and lasting partnerships across academia, as well as with the next generation of communicators, is essential to advancing feminist media goals. To sustain this commitment, we promote the creation of a European student network that would provide a platform for young researchers to engage in ongoing conversations and workshops, equipping them to critically engage with and update the objectives of the Beijing Platform for Action for future generations.

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